

Quantum Average Momentum Compared with Classical Statistical Pressure Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 16, 2023

In Part I, we considered the ideal gas law $P = \text{density}(x) RT$ of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, which follows from the notion of impulse $2p$ multiplied by v (flux) and then averaged, and examined how it balanced (on two sides of a box) a force $-dV(x)/dx$ multiplied by density. We argued that in a quantum bound state there is no notion of internal time and hence no flux and so considered an average impulse $2p$ multiplied by an overall internal time in the system, namely \hbar/E . We found that this scenario balanced with $-dV/dx$ matches the quantum oscillator ground state.

In this note we ask: What about other potential $V(x)$ situations? Quantum mechanics seems to be a mixture of statistical mechanics and Newtonian dynamics i.e. the time-independent Schrodinger equation is, on average, an energy conservation equation for all energy levels i.e. $KE(x)+V(x) = E_n$ where $KE = \frac{\sum_p a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(kpx)}{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)}$. In (1) we took d/dx to bring out a force term $-dV/dx$ and showed it is linked to $\langle p^2/2m \rangle$ and $\langle p^2/2m \rangle \langle p \rangle$, but analyzed these in terms of fluxes. The notion of flux makes sense using external time, but internally there is no time and so here we try to examine the situation in terms of various impulses.

Motivation for Considering Impulses in Quantum Mechanics

It is well known that the free particle quantum wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar d/dx$ and $-1/2m d^2/dx^2$ yielding classical eigenvalues p and $p^2/2m$. As a result, one might think it describes classical physics, but this is only the case if there is no interference and if one uses external time. In particular, $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ and both $\sin(px)$ and $\cos(px)$ represent spatial probability distributions linked to internal acceleration, we argue. Only on average does $x = p/m t$. If $x = p/m t$ were the whole picture there would be no interference, but this is experimentally observed in a two slit experiment. Furthermore, the quantum free particle interacts with the two slit mechanism suggesting the notion of force/acceleration.

On the other hand, an impulse hit from a quantum free particle at any point within a wavelength \hbar/p is $2p$. The spatial probability distribution does not seem to change this as follows from Einstein's 1905 photoelectric results. As a result, we ask: How may one think of a particle in a single quantum bound state in terms of impulses?

Two Pieces to Quantum Impulses

In Part I we examined the classical statistical mechanics case for which an ideal gas law holds i.e. $P(x) = \text{density}(x)RT$ together with a potential $V(x)$. Each single gas particle follows Newton's energy conservation law $p^2/2m + V(x) = E$, but in addition, two particle collisions occur (associated with T temperature) so macroscopic chunks of gas are considered to be at rest. From Newton's law one may balance pressure on the two walls of a box with the force $-dV/dx$ acting on the density within the box. Thus:

$$d/dx \text{ density}(x) RT = -dV/dx \text{ density}(x) \quad ((1))$$

In Part I we noted how ((1)) may be obtained by simply considering information loss, first for two particle collisions, and then for a single particle at x_1 and x_2 using the notion of conservation of energy for a single particle.

Next, we tried to create a quantum analogy, but argued that (A) there is no internal time quantum mechanically so one cannot create a pressure average internally using $2p \cdot v = \text{impulse} \cdot \text{flux}$ because there is no notion of flux internally. As a result, we calculated an average impulse $2p$ and multiplied it by $1/\tau$ an average internal time, namely E_n/\hbar . We found that such a scheme matched the quantum oscillator ground state.

What about other $V(x)$ values and other states? Quantum mechanics seems to be statistical in nature as one creates averages using the ensemble $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ (which involves interference), but on the other hand average energy follows Newton's conservation of energy equation for any energy level i.e.

$$KE(x)+V(x) = E_n \text{ where } KE = \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)pp/2m \exp(kpx)\}/\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)\}. \quad ((2))$$

Thus there seem to be two pieces:

(A) An analogue to pressure due to the distribution $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ changing with x

(B) Deterministic motion due to energy conservation which is also linked to impulse

One may note that the notion of impulse follows from Newton's second law $dp/dt = F$ or $\text{Integral } dp = \text{Integral } F \ dt$. Thus a bound Newtonian particle is associated with an impulse at each x , but this is not usually multiplied by a flux v to calculate pressure. If one did so, however then:

$$Dp \ v = dp \ p/m \ \text{integrates to} \ \ p^2/2m = \text{kinetic energy} \quad ((3))$$

There is no averaging because there is a single p value at each x .

Thus kinetic energy is like a pressure term which is balanced with $V(x)$ to yield a constant E at each x . To examine this in terms of force ($dp/dt=F$):

$$d/dx \ p^2/2m = -dV/dx \ \text{or} \ p/m \ dp/dx = -dV/dx \quad ((4))$$

Thus unlike classical statistical mechanics where one has pressure on two sides of a box balancing $-dV/dx \cdot \text{density}$ because particles move in both directions, ((4)) shows that:

$$p/m \ dp = v \ \text{impulse} = -dV/dx \ dx \quad ((5))$$

This is similar to the quantum scenario where there is also no "little box" of statistical mechanics.

Nonrelativistic Quantum Bound State

We now wish to examine a Newtonian conservative force $-dV/dx$ in a quantum single particle bound state. In (1) we showed:

$$-dV/dx = \frac{1}{2m} \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ ppp \right\} / W(x) + KE(x) (-dW/dx/W) \quad ((6))$$

We analyzed this in terms of fluxes, but within a quantum system we argue that fluxes do make sense as there is no internal time. As a result, we would like to see if ((6)) may be interpreted in terms of impulses.

We start with the example of a particle in a box with infinite walls such that $-dV/dx=0$ in the interior. The wavefunction is $A \sin(pave \ x)$ where $pave = n\pi/L$ which demonstrates a spatial probability in x and thus, we argue, a force/acceleration due to density, somewhat like $PV=nRT$ in a MB gas. This seems to be linked to the second term on the RHS in ((6)) where

$$-dW/dx/W = | -id/dx \ W / W | = \text{average impulse} \quad \text{and} \quad KE(x) = 1/\text{average time} \quad ((7))$$

Using the notion of energy being $1/\text{time}$. The second term on the RHS of ((6)) is based on the derivative of $1/W(x)$ which shows that probability changes with x and so is related in a sense to $PV=nRT$.

The first term on the RHS of ((6)), however, cancels the second term and is linked with unnormalized kinetic energy changing with x which is also related to force. How may one interpret $\langle ppp/2m \rangle$? One may argue that instead of considering average impulse multiplied by an average internal time as in ((7)), one may consider the impulse of each single particle where $pp/2m$ from $\exp(-pp/2m \ t \ i)$ represents $1/\text{time}$ for the single particle. Thus, nonrelativistically $\langle ppp/2m \rangle$ is an average over single particle impulses multiplied by their unique internal times. It may be noted that in the Newtonian mechanics of a bound particle, dp is the impulse, but in the quantum case a free particle does not accelerate so there is no dp and also no flux v .

The question becomes: Why do the two terms in ((6)) cancel? The first term on the RHS of ((6)) represents a change in unnormalized kinetic energy at x as the particle moves to $x+dx$. A negative sign is introduced by $d/dx \ 1/W(x)$ so the change in probability $W(x)$ with x counters the change in unnormalized kinetic energy. This is like an action/reaction balance, we argue. Both impulse terms are present, but cancel because overall there is no average force or acceleration in the picture i.e. $-dV/dx=0$.

For the situation in which a $V(x)$ is present, the two terms in ((6)) yields $-dV/dx$, thus the reaction "pressure" from a change in probability $W(x)$ cannot cancel fully the single particle averaged action impulse.

Oscillator Ground State Case

What happens in the oscillator ground state for which $E_0 = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{k/m}$ and $W(x) = C \exp(-\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{k/m} x^2)$?

The first term on the RHS of ((6)) is: $(-dV/dx) - \sqrt{k/m} x (E-V(x))$

The second term on the RHS of ((6)) is: $(E-V(x)) \sqrt{k/m} x$ which is the pressure type term due to density i.e. a change in $W(x)$.

The formalism above, however, applies to any potential and energy level i.e.

The first term on the RHS of ((6)) is: $-dV/dx + (E-V) dW/dx / W$

The second term on the RHS of ((6)) is: $-(E-V) dW/dx / W$

Thus one sees the action/reaction pieces cancel leaving $-dV/dx$ which represents an average acceleration of $\langle p/m \rangle$ as in the Newtonian case.

The unique feature of the ground state oscillator, however, is that $E^2 dW/dx / W = -dV/dx$. This, however, is neither the first or second term on the RHS side of ((6)). Thus, it seems that a key feature of the oscillator state is that the average impulse i.e. $dW/dx / W$ is proportional to x and so to $-dV/dx$ with average time being a constant i.e. \hbar/E . This mimics the formalism of classical statistical mechanics i.e. of an MB gas with a potential $V(x)$. (At the same, however, the $\langle p^2/2m \rangle$ and $\langle p/2m \rangle \langle p \rangle$ formalism also holds.)

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the time-independent Schrodinger equation and take d/dx as in (1) to obtain an equation for $-dV/dx = \text{force}(x)$ in terms of quantum impulses. This leads to two terms: $\langle p^2/2m \rangle$ and $\langle p/2m \rangle \langle p \rangle$. We argue that in a quantum bound state there is no internal time so the $2pv$ which is averaged in classical statistical mechanics (e.g. an MB gas) to obtain pressure cannot be used as there is no $v = \text{flux}$ term. Instead, one needs to find an internal time value so that $1/\text{internal time} * \int F dt$ allows for the time values to cancel. $\langle p^2/2m \rangle$ seems to consider the internal time associated with each free particle in the ensemble $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ namely $1/t = E = p^2/2m$ from $\exp(-ipx) \exp(-ipx)$. This, however, is counteracted by $\langle p/2m \rangle \langle p \rangle$ where $\langle p \rangle$ is like an average impulse multiplied by $KE(x)$ as the $1/\text{internal time}$. This effect is due strictly to the density changing i.e. $W(x)$ changing from one x to another and so is similar to the classical statistical mechanical effect of changing density balancing force. In the case of $-dV/dx = 0$ as in a box with infinite potential walls, the two terms cancel, but in general they do not. The ground state oscillator is interesting in that the density piece i.e. $d/dx (1/W)$ is proportional to the force which mimics the scenario in classical MB gas, although at the same time the two pieces $\langle p^2/2m \rangle$ and $\langle p/2m \rangle \langle p \rangle$ still exists.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Fluxes in Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2018)